

FORMATION AND CONSOLIDATION OF CARBON / POLYCARBONATE TOWPREGS

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ABSTRACT

A powder coating technique was used to form towpregs from carbon fibres and a thermoplastic matrix. Composite specimens were fabricated from the towpreg and then subject to mechanical testing. Finally, the mechanical properties of these composites were determined and compared with theoretical predictions using the Classical Lamination Theory (CLT).

The objective of this study was to assess the advantages and disadvantages of the powder coating technique as compared to existing technologies for producing thermoplastic matrix composites.

INTRODUCTION

Because of their excellent properties, long fibre thermoplastic matrix composite materials have been successfully employed in aircraft and aerospace applications. In these and many other commercial engineering applications, they can replace other materials, such as thermoset composites. The principal advantages are: excellent toughness, durability and damping properties, easier storage, reshaping, reparability and more favourable recycling and processing routes which do not involve chemical reactions [1,2]. However, the high cost of the impregnation of long fibre thermoplastic composites, caused by the melting of the polymer or the use of solvents, still restricts their use in non-aerospace applications. Cost reduction largely depends on developing more efficient ways of impregnating fibres with high-viscosity thermoplastics. Also, as many commercial applications do not require maximum mechanical and thermal specifications, the use of cheaper matrices and lower reinforcement fractions represents another way of reducing costs.

A dry coating process was developed for economic application of a high-viscosity matrices to fibre tows. This technique produces a flexible pre-impregnated material, which can be woven, braided, knitted or cut before the processing by hot compression moulding [3,4]. Using this process, a polycarbonate powder was deposited onto PAN based carbon fibre tows, and a carbon/polycarbonate (C/PC) towpreg with moderate fibre volume fractions (*ca.* 25%) was obtained. Polycarbonate was chosen as the matrix due to its i) good mechanical properties and

established use in engineering applications; ii) good adherence to carbon fibres [5], iii) moderate price and, iv) its amorphous character leading to a morphology which is not very affected by the thermal gradients during moulding. Moreover, the excellent impact behaviour of polycarbonate is an additional feature for many engineering applications.

THEORY

According to the Classical Lamination Theory (CLT) [6-8], the stress/strain relationship for a laminate, using a laminate related co-ordinate system, is given by:

$$\{\epsilon^o\}_{xy} = [\alpha^*] \{\sigma^o\}_{xy} + \frac{[\beta^*]}{3} \{\sigma^f\}_{xy}$$

and

$$\{\epsilon^f\}_{xy} = [\beta^{*T}] \{\sigma^o\}_{xy} + [\delta^*] \{\sigma^f\}_{xy}$$
(1)

where: $[\alpha^*] = h [\alpha]$, $[\beta^*] = \frac{h^2[\beta]}{2}$ and $[\delta^*] = \frac{h^3[\delta]}{12}$ are the normalised compliance matrices, h is the total laminate thickness;

$\{\epsilon^o\}_{xy}$ and $\{\epsilon^f\}_{xy} = \frac{h}{2} \{k\}_{xy}$, are the laminate mid plane and outer surface strains, $\{\sigma^o\}_{xy}$ and $\{\sigma^f\}_{xy}$, are the normalised mid plane and flexural stresses, and $[\alpha]$, $[\beta]$ and $[\delta]$, are the compliance matrices.

The laminate compliance matrices were calculated using engineering constants E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , and ν_{12} derived on the basis of the fibre and the matrix volume fractions of each laminae.

The apparent modulus of elasticity of the laminate in the x-direction was calculated as

$$E_x = \frac{1}{\alpha_{11}}$$
(2)

The laminate failure was predicted by the Tsai-Hill criterion, assuming the First Ply Failure principle. Accordingly, the laminate failure occurs when, for any ply:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_1 \cdot \sigma_2}{X^2} + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 = 1$$
(3)

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the principal tensile stresses in the ply, τ_{12} the maximum shear stress in the ply, and, X , Y and S , are the ultimate principal stresses and the ultimate shear stress of the ply

The ultimate principal stresses for each ply were predicted according to [6]:

$$X = \sigma_f \nu_f \quad Y = \sigma_m \cdot (1 - 2 \sqrt{\frac{\nu_f}{\pi}}) \quad S = \tau_m \left[1 - (\sqrt{\nu_f} - \nu_f) \left(1 - \frac{G_m}{G_f} \right) \right]$$
(4)

where the subscripts m and f refer to the fibres and to the matrix, respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

Towpregs were formed from PAN based carbon fibres (Thornel T300/12/NT, produced by Amoco Performance Products, Inc.) and a polycarbonate matrix (Makrolon 5308, produced by Bayer). Prior to coating, the polycarbonate was ground to powder. The principal properties of the fibres are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Carbon fibre properties

Property	Units	Value
Density	Mg/m ³	1.76
Tensile strength	GPa	3.5
Tensile modulus	GPa	230
Strain at break	%	1.5
Specific tow weight	g/m	0.797

POWDER COATING LINE

The coating line shown schematically in Fig. 1 was used to produce the C/PC towpregs. This apparatus had been previously developed at the Center for Advanced Engineering Fibers at Clemson University (South Carolina, U.S.A.) [3, 9-12].

Figure 1- Schematic diagram of powder coating line [11].

During the process, the fibre tow is pulled by the wind-off mechanism, passed through a dancer arm which controls the fibre tow tension, and the filaments spread over a comb using a pneumatic device. This spread tow is covered with the thermoplastic in the deposition chamber, where a powder cloud is generated by an electrical fan. Next, the coated tow is passed through a tube furnace, which softens the thermoplastic causing it to adhere to the fibres. Finally, the coated tow is cooled and wound-up.

The C/PC towpregs were produced using the operating conditions shown in Table 2. During production the towpreg quality was controlled by monitoring the specific towpreg weight, d_{tow} .

Table 2- Coating line operating conditions

Variable	Units	Value
Linear tow speed	m/min	2,5-3
Powder feed rate	m ³ /min	26 x 10 ⁻³
Fan speed	rpm	3500
Furnace temperature	°C	320
Pneumatic pressure on the spreader	kPa	70

The mass fraction, w_f , of carbon fibre in the towpreg is calculated as:

$$w_f = \frac{d_{lin}}{d_{tow}} \quad (5)$$

where d_{lin} is the specific tow weight.

Processing conditions were varied to yield fibre mass fractions between 27% and 45%, corresponding to fibre volume fractions between 20% and 31%.

TOWPREG CONSOLIDATION

The technique developed by Albiger [10] was followed to lay-up the composites specimens. This technique utilised a wrapping wire mandrel (Fig. 2) to facilitate the towpreg lay-up. The towpreg spool is mounted onto a horizontal bar and the coated tow is wrapped around the mandrel by rotating end-over-end. One deficiency of this procedure is that the fibres are not rigorously aligned in the final lay-up.

Figure 2. Wrapping technique used for towpreg lay-up.

To increase its flexibility, the coated tow is placed between two hot rods and heated at 260°C for 5 minutes. After cooling, the tow lay-up is cut with a knife, creating a preform with the dimensions of the mould. Finally, the preform is placed in the mould. A 400 kN SATIM hot

platen press was used to consolidate the final C/PC towpreg. The press is equipped with two independently controlled electrical heaters, and an automatic air/water cooling system. The composite C/PC towpreg mouldings (157 mm x 112 mm x 2 mm plates) were produced with a prototype steel semi-positive compression mould. The moulding conditions used are shown in Table 3.

Table 3- Consolidation conditions

Variable	Units	Value
Platen temperature	°C	260
Pressure on the material surface	MPa	8
Compression time	min	10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of the PC Powder

The dimensions and size distribution of the PC powder were determined by image analysis. After initial observations were made using a light transmission microscope Olympus BH-2, the images were analysed with a video camera JVC TK 1280 connected to a Leica Quantimet 500 image analyser software. Table 4 gives the final summary of the average results of 977 particle measurements.

Table 4. Image analysis results from microscopy observations

	Area (μm^2)	Length (μm)	Width (μm)	Aspect ratio	Equiv. diam (μm)
Mean	19525,3	184,6	101,4	2,12	113,6
Std Dev	39516,3	188,2	113,9	0,86	109,3
Max.	364928	1233,6	815,2	8	681,6
Min	118,1	10,9	5,4	1,1	12,3

These observations showed that the PC particles did not have a circular shape (as suggested by the aspect ratio values) and that the particle sizes varied over a very wide range. A typical sample of the PC powder used in this work is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Particle shapes of PC powder under the light microscope (58x)

Towpreg Characterisation by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Several samples of C/PC towpreg were analysed with a Leica S360 Scanning electron microscope to further evaluate the distribution of the PC powder and its adhesion to the fibres. Figure 4 shows two SEM micrographs of the gold coated towpreg. At higher magnification (a), the polymer is seen to wet and envelope the carbon fibres, implying a good adhesion. The particles are quasi-circular, a consequence of the surface tension of the softened polycarbonate. At lower magnification (b), shows that the polymer is irregularly distributed over the towpreg. In previous work, Klett suggested that irregular distribution can occur if there is a wide distribution in particle size [11]. The large size distribution appears to promote agglomeration, and the agglomerated powder irregularly coats the fibre tow.

Figure 4. Distribution of PC powder on the carbon towpreg
SEM magnifications: a) 250 \times , b) 35 \times

Composite Cross-Section Evaluation using Reflection Microscopy

To assess the presence of voids and the regularity of the fibre distribution in the composites, several composite samples were cross-sectioned transverse to the fibre orientation. The polished cross-sections were observed by reflected light microscopy using an Olympus BH-2 microscope. As Fig. 5 illustrates, no voids were observed.

Figure 5. Composite cross-section (116 \times)

Nevertheless, irregularities were observed in the fibre distribution (areas quite rich in fibres contrasting with areas rich in matrix). This may have been the result of the irregular distribution of powder onto the towpreg surface, as previously suggested.

Tensile Testing

The tensile properties of the polycarbonate matrix used were determined at room temperature with an Instron 4505 universal testing machine using 150 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm type I test pieces (according to ISO 3268/78). These samples were obtained from compression moulded plates formed from the powder material. The testing was conducted at a cross-head speed of 5 mm/min using a static extensometer. The final test results are shown in Table 5. Similar tests were performed on tensile test pieces cut from the composites with fibres aligned parallel to the applied load, using a crosshead rate of displacement of 2 mm/min.

Table 5. Tensile Properties

Property	Units	Material		
		Polycarbonate	C/PC towpreg	
Tensile strength*	MPa	Mean value	62.79	404.0
		Std devn.	1.85	46.3
Tensile modulus	GPa	Mean value	2.33	58.4
		Std devn.	0.12	5.8
Strain at break	%		>100	0.75

* For polycarbonate - yield stress
 For the composite - stress at break

The experimental results for the composite should correspond to the properties in the principal direction 1. The tensile properties of the unidirectional composite can be predicted using Eqns. 1 to 4. Hence, considering a fibre volume fraction of $v_f = 0.25$, $E_f = 230$ GPa, $v_m = 0.27$, $\sigma_f = 3500$ MPa, $E_m = 2.33$ GPa, $v_m = 0.38$ and $\sigma_m = 62.8$ MPa, one may obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ultimate tensile strength (X)} &= 875 \text{ MPa} \\ \text{Tensile modulus (E}_1\text{)} &= 59.25 \text{ GPa} \\ \text{Maximum tensile strain (}\epsilon_1^{\text{max}}\text{)} &= 1.5 \% \end{aligned}$$

A significant difference is observed between the predicted ultimate tensile strength and strain, and the experimental values. However, the 18 mm wide strips of the towpreg (see Fig. 1) are not precisely oriented at 0°. Instead, in some layers they are slightly misaligned at 6°. For example, if a four layer composite is fabricated, a laminate (0°/0°/6°/-6°)_T is obtained. In this case, a CLT software would predict:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ultimate tensile strength (}\sigma_x\text{)} &= 527.5 \text{ MPa} \\ \text{Tensile Modulus (E}_x\text{)} &= 57.14 \text{ GPa} \\ \text{Maximum tensile strain (}\epsilon_x^{\text{max}}\text{)} &= 0.92 \% \end{aligned}$$

These predicted values are much closer to those obtained experimentally (see Table 5). Thus, the slight misalignment caused by the laying-up technique appears to account for much of the difference between the measured strength and that predicted for a perfectly aligned specimen.

CONCLUSIONS

This work showed that the towpreg technique can be applied to form thermoplastic matrix based composites with a somewhat reduced volume fibre fraction (25%). The technique produces composites with no voids and an excellent fibre-polymer adhesion. This was confirmed by the close agreement between experimental values and predictions based on the Classical Lamination Theory. Slight discrepancies appear to be the result of misalignment of the fibres during the fabrication process.

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